

David Gerber, MD, MHS, FRCS(C), is a gynecologist who has been practicing since 1997. He is currently a [leading labiaplasty surgeon](#). Previously, he worked in isolated Manitoba and Alberta as a family physician.

He graduated from Stellenbosch University in South Africa with a medical degree. He worked in a large rural hospital in Ciskei (an underprivileged neighborhood), focusing on internal medicine, obstetrics, and gynecology after his internship in Cape Town. During [his training at the University of British Columbia](#) in Vancouver, he specialized in Obstetrics and Gynecology. In Toronto, he completed a subspecialty in Incontinence Surgery after completing his residency at the University of British Columbia. At the University of Toronto, he earned a Master of Health Sciences in bioethics in 2004.

At Sunnybrook and Women's College Health Science Centre in Toronto, he specialized in minimally invasive surgery, colposcopy, and emergency gynecology.

Besides his success as a micro-surgery specialist for labia reduction surgery, [Dr David Gerber](#) also has extensive experience specializing in minimally invasive clinic-based surgery for fibroids, heavy vaginal bleeding, vulva disease, and precancerous lesions (abnormal pap tests) of the vulva, vagina, and cervix.

Dr David Gerber is passionate about labiaplasty and the psychological and physical changes that it can bring to a person. He is a board-certified plastic surgeon in Toronto, CA, who helps women from all over the Toronto area feel happier and more confident through vaginal rejuvenation.